

Designing a Video Script of New Ocarina as One of Tourism Destination in Batam

Syamarah Humairo Viranda

McDermott, Batam, Indonesia

Email address: syamarahhumairoviranda@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT: The aim of this research was to know how to design a video of New Ocarina as one of tourism destination in Batam using the steps of writing a script by Hanifa (2013). The methodology of this research was Research and Development Method (R&D) adapted from Plomp (1997). The steps were: (1) Preliminary Investigation, (2) Designing, (3) Realization/Construction, (4) Test, evaluation, and revision, (5) Implementation. In the preliminary investigation, the writer did a literature study and field study. In designing, the writer designs the script using Jakacaping (2018) format. Then, there is realization/construction. In this step the writer make first draft. After that, the writer did testing, evaluation, and revision by gave it to 5 experts. The experts were evaluating and giving comments to the script and video. After that the writer revised the script and the video. In conclusion the writer could make a script that has been testified by using Hanifa (2013) of steps writing script and research and methodology by Plomp (1997).

Keywords: *Video, Script, Tourism destination*

INTRODUCTION

New Ocarina is located at Sadai, Kecamatan Bengkong, Kota Batam, Kepulauan Riau. This tourism destination was inaugurated by the president of Indonesia Susilo Bambang Yudhoyono in January 2009. As the name Batam New Ocarina Mega Tourism, this place does have an area of about 40 hectares. Originally, in the New Ocarina area, there are around 18 types of rides, cottages, nature tourism, and the best facilities offered to visitors. Not only adrenaline rides can be felt, but also relax, have picnics with family and even interact directly with the sea.

This place provides several rides, such as a kids' zone and a Giant wheel. When we are at its peak point, we will see the entire New Ocarina Mega tourism area and a view of half the city of Batam. Then there are Extreme Sky runners, Spin tower, Balloon Castle, Climbing Net, Bicycle Rental, Aero Rail, Park Train, Water Park, Robot Rail, 360 Madness, and others. Then there is nature tourism. Visitors could swim on the beach and visitors can also fish there,

because this tourist spot is directly adjacent to the sea.

This Mega tourism also provides restaurants and sells food, drinks, and snacks. This place put the safety first for the visitor that is why in every play zone there must have guards at least 2 or 3 people including the operator man and security to pay attention when the ride is in progress.

This place greatly affects economic development in the tourism sector. According to Wahab (2003) Tourism is one type of new industry that is able to generate rapid economic growth in the provision of jobs, standards life and stimulate other productivity sectors.

To expand information about this tour, a unique and interesting promotion is needed to attract tourist to visit this tourist attraction. Nowadays, there are a lot of ways to promote something especially with social media. So, to persuade more people to visit New Ocarina Batam, the writer would love to make a video script to give explanation and information to public about New Ocarina Mega Tourism. By making the video script and uploading to social media such as Instagram and YouTube, the writer believed this video would help increase the visitor to come and help the economy in the city of Batam.

Based on the explanation above, the writer wants to introduce various advantages of this New Ocarina tourist attraction by designing a video script that contains an explanation of the facilities, existing rides and nature tourism in there, so that it can provide information to readers about this attraction and can also help increase the interest of tourists to visit New Ocarina Batam, especially during the pandemic that has occurred in the past few years. The Writer would like to write the final report entitled Designing Video Script of New Ocarina as One of Tourism Destinations in Batam. Based on the background information above, problem

formulation of this report is “How to make a video script of New Ocarina as one of tourism destinations in Batam?”

LITERATURE REVIEW

Definition of Video

According to McFarland (2014) video is a powerful tool for promotion he mentions several advantages of video they are:

- a. Video has become so easy to use that a person can simply use a Smartphone, tablet or computer to record a video.
- b. Video is an impeccable storytelling medium that allows the viewer to look and listen to the content, using multiple senses that have the ability to transport your mind from the environment you are in and place you inside the environment of the video.
- c. Video is being watched online more and more every year including an 800% increase in online video consumption over the past six years, a 55% majority of video news viewers among Internet users and 2 billion video views per week are monetized on YouTube.

In addition, video is any media format that employs a cathode-ray screen to present the picture portion of the message can be referred to as video. Moreover, Arsyad, (2004: 36) in Rusman (2011: 218), “video is a series of motion pictures accompanied by sound that forms a unity that is strung together into a flow, with messages in it for the achievement of learning objectives that are stored by the process of storage on tape or disk media. In addition, video is an audio-visual media that displays motion.”

Based on the understanding according to some experts above, it can be concluded that video is one type of audio-visual media and can describe an object that moves together with

natural sound or the appropriate sound. The video present's information, explains the process, explains complicated concepts, teaches skills, shortens or extends time, and influences attitude.

Definition of Tourism

Many kinds of activities done by people to enjoy life and refresh brain from common activities in their work or daily activities such as fishing, watching TV or movie, gathering friends and many others. One of those activities is tourism. Based on Indonesia dictionary, Tourism is an activity associated with leisure travel. According to Soekadijo (2003), tourism means that displacement of people for a while to destinations outside the places where they normally live and work, and their activities during stay at the destination While Meyers (2009) states that tourism is a travel activity carried out temporarily from the original place of residence to the destination area with the reason not to settle or make a living but only to fulfill curiosity, spend leisure or holiday and other destinations.

Video Script

According to Norbury (2014) script is “sequences of actions or events” presenting focal ideas and can be synchronized with other context scripts. Video script is crucial to help readers and viewers comprehend text.

2.4. Steps of Script Writing

Based on Hanifa (2013) stages of script writing usually consists of activities, they are:

- a. Formulate an idea. The idea of a story that will be made into a video and television program can be taken from a true story (true story) or non-fiction and fiction or fiction.
- b. Research. Research in this context is an attempt to study and gather information related

to the text to be written. Information sources can be in the form of books, newspapers or other publications and people or resource persons who can provide accurate information about the contents or substance to be written.

c. Outline. Outlines generally contain an outline of information that you will write into a script.

d. Synopsis. The synopsis must be clear so that it can give an idea of the contents of the video or television program we are going to make.

e. Treatment. A treatment must contain a clear description of the location, time, player, scene and property that will be recorded into the video program.

f. Script writing. Although in writing a script the writer can make changes, but the changes made should not be changes that are substantive. Change should be creative and not change the substance of the program.

g. Script Review. Draft manuscripts that have been completed need to be reviewed to see the truth of the substance and also the way of delivering the message. The draft script must be reviewed by people who understand the substance of program content (content experts) and who understand the media (media specialist).

h. Finalize the Finalization of the script is the final step before the manuscript is submitted to the producer and director to be produced. The final paper is the result of a revision of the input provided by content experts and media experts.

METHOD

In this research, the writer used research and development methodology of Plomp

(1997). The Plomp model is seen as more flexible compared to other models. Therefore, the researcher chose to use Plomp model research design. Plomp model consists of five phases or 5 stages, namely: preliminary investigation phase, design, realization/construction, (test, evaluation, and revision), and implementation. The stages in the Plomp model, it can be described as follows:

Chart 3.1.Steps of R&D Methods Developed Source: Plomp (1997)

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1. Preliminary Investigation

In field survey, the writer went to New Ocarina Mega Tourism location. The writer looked for the information by collecting data through observation, interview with the manager of New Ocarina and documentation. The information is about facilities, tourist attraction and others object offered there. This data collection serves to strengthen the background of the problem, the purpose of the research, and its benefits.

2. Designing

After the writer got the complete data from preliminary investigation stage, the writer tried to use the format of video script by Jakacaping (2018) to write the script that consist of four elements, which are hook, introduction, body and closing. Then, for the software the writer used final draft for the script as the software. The writer also reads some books and online articles related to video script, especially on how to write video script and make it in a good format.

3. Realization/Construction

In this phase, the basic form of the product is produced as a result of the realization of the product design phase. The writer made the first draft from the script arrangement in previous stage. The first draft was containing the information about facilities, tourist attraction and object.

4. Testing, evaluation, and revision

In this step, the script that the writer made has tested, evaluated, and revised the product. The testing, evaluation, and revision of this research will be chosen by the knowledge and skills of the participants possess. The participants included some experts such as graphic design, scriptwriting, tourism, linguistic and language experts.

5. Implementation

After evaluation and obtaining a valid product, the product can be implemented for a wider area. According to Plomp (1997) solutions have to be introduced, in other words, have to be implemented. After testing the product succeed and there are no revisions again, the product in

the form of videos can be disseminated on YouTube to preserve New Ocarina Mega Tourism.

3.2. Place of Research

The place of research must be clearly identified in order to obtain valid and correct data and information. The research will be conducted in New Ocarina. This place is located in Sadai, Bengkong District, Batam City, Riau Islands.

3.3. Technique of Collecting Data

In this research, the writer use observation, interview, and documentation

a. Primary Sources.

The primary source is the data source that directly provides data for data collectors. The primary source of this form of notes of interviews was obtained through interviews conducted by the author.

b. Secondary Sources.

The secondary data sources are data sources that do not provide information directly to the data collector. This secondary data sources can be the result of further processing of primary data presented in another form or from another person. This data is used to support the information from primary data obtained either from the interviews, as well as from direct observation to the field.

In documentation, the writer will used writing and videos for documentation. Writing itself is about the content of the script and the videos related to the video script and other videos that will be compared. The writer will used camera in document the collecting data.

Technique of Analyzing Data

After collecting all the data that will be collected and processed by the writer, the result of data presentation is informally presentation through observation, interview to informants served by providing explanation, so the results can answer the problem. The writer records some videos in New Ocarina to know the real situation there. After all, the writer saves it as reference to support the data of the research.

After the writer got the information about the content, the data were processed into three steps: Listening to the interviewee's answer and transcribing it, making the necessary information to be included in the script, paraphrasing and translating the information.

1. Documentation

In this step the writer has gathered and selected some sources related to the topic of the research. Collecting data from several sources can help the writer to determine ideas and themes that will be made. The writer found the data from two sources

- a. Primary sources. In this phase the writer found about the information directly to the location and had the interview with manager of New Ocarina. The writer asked some questions about facilities, object, visitors, and tourist attraction. After that, the writer collected it and made some notes.
- b. Secondary sources. This phase is when the writer gathered the information indirectly or from observing the information from primary sources. The writer also was looking some of sources by several authors from the internet. There are e-journal: Research and development (r&d) method as a model design in educational research and its alternative by Gustiani (2019) Doctoral dissertation by Rahmawati, A. (2020) with title A

promotional video script of Palembang blongket, e-article Mega wisata Costarina Batam web: tujuanwisatanasional [Blog post] By Martial, Anthony, (2020 October 28). Then the writer arranged it into the script writing.

FINDINGS

The writer use Plomp, 1997 model as cited in Gustiani, (2019) as the research and development method. There are 5 stages that use in Plomp models

DRAFT	REVISION
Want to try a lot of rides with a beautiful beach view? but don't want to go to many places?	Want to try a lot of rides with a beautiful beach view but don't want to go to many places?
Let's go to New Ocarina Batam"	Let's go to New Ocarina Batam!"
Batam is one of my favourite cities to relax. In Batam, it has various destinations,	Batam is one of my favourite cities to relax. It has various destinations,
This tour is in 15 kilometres from Singapore. "Wow, just imagine the view! It must be cool". starting from IDR 15,000, You can feel the	This destination is 15 kilometres from Singapore. "Wow, just imagine the view! It must be cool". Starting from IDR 15,000,00,- you can feel the excitement of the rides you want to
excitement of the rides you want to try. This destination has an area of about 35-40 hectares, making it one of the largest tourist attractions in the city of Batam.	try. This destination has an area of about 35-40 hectares, making it one of the largest tourist attractions in the city of Batam
New Ocarina presents a combination of natural beach tourism, culinary tourism, a variety of contemporary rides in the same area, and has modern style.	New Ocarina presents a combination of natural beach tourism, culinary tourism, a variety of contemporary rides, and a modern style.
"These shio statuea are also one of the Instagrammable photospots."	"These shio statues are also one of the Instagrammable photospots."
This tour presents 18 kinds of rides,	New Ocarina presents 18 kinds of rides,

One of the rides that visitors must try is the giant wheel	one of the rides thatvisitors must-try is the giant wheel,
Friends, fish or swim on the beach. “Wow, that’s really fun, right? I can’t wait to go there!”	Friends, go fishing or swim on the beach. “Wow,that’s really fun,right? I can’t wait togo there!”
“Wow, it’s really funso, there’s no need to provide a carpet to relax on. How about the security? Don’t worry inNew Ocarina, the Security	So, you don’t need to provide a mat to relax on. How about the security? Don’t worry! In New Ocarina, the security
It’s really fun, isn’t it? The place is also cool and spacious.	“It sounds fun! Right? The place is also cool and spacious.
It’s very interesting,isn’t it? What are you waiting for? If you are travelling to Batam,don’t forget, New Ocarina must be the first stop on your list to visit.”	This is a sign for you to come and travel to Batam. What are you waiting for? New Ocarinamust be the first stopon your list to visit.”

Implementation

Implementation	Steps of writing script
	Finalization

Implementation is the last stage of Plomp model. After completed the other stages, the writer got the final draft of the script. The product that has been test and being the final product then uploaded on YouTube as the online media platform. The writer choose YouTube platform, because the uses of YouTube are increasing these days around the world.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The discussion informed the process of video script writing. In this final report, the writer do the research based on five steps of Research and Development by Plomp(1997) there are preliminary investigation, designing, realization/construction, (testing

evaluation and revision), and implementation. The writer also uses steps of script writing by Hanifa (2013). The steps are formulated idea, research, and outline. Besides, this step followed by several steps, the steps are selecting the material, planning the content, arrangement, first draft, revision and final draft.

The writer made the script based on the Elements of Script Writing by Jakacaping (2018). First, the writer made the hook that aims for viewers to attract the video. After that is introduction, it consist the general information. Then, the writer make the body of the script, it consist the main information. And the last is closing, in closing part the writer made persuasive sentences. Since the research and made the script has done, the writer was not found the trouble, because the information that obtained is clearly.

For script the writer give to script writing expert Ms. Hasna Fatina Sakinah Abdul Kadir. She was checking the grammatical error and proper sentences. Then, Mr. Adi Sustrisman S.Kom and Mr. Kemas Latief as the Head of DPD HPI Sumsel was checking the content of video, after accepted the comments and suggestions from the experts, the writer revised the script correctly and finished the final product. Next, the writer uploaded the video in the social media YouTube platforms. In YouTube, the writer made a thumbnail forthe YouTube video to get viewer's attention. The writer hopes that this video becomes one of media to introduce New Ocarina as one of tourism attraction in Batam.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

There were Preliminary investigations, designing, realization / construction, testing evaluating and revision, the last one is implementation. Afte the writer did research with those step, the writer know that the video script can beused as a guideline for tourists and

visitors to find information about New Ocarina. This video consists of information about New Ocarina such as the location, the transportation, the attraction, the activities, the facilities, and the prices. The duration of the video is 6 minutes and 9 seconds. This video is bilingual because the narrator used English language and Indonesian language as the subtitles.

The writer has some suggestions to the scriptwriter in South Sumatera. In making script, they have to make a new innovation in choosing the concept they want to turn into a script. The writer suggests the scriptwriter increase the number of the script from the tourism in Batam. In addition, the writer also would like to suggest the government to pay more attention to tourism that has the potential to compete in the tourism industry. Furthermore, new ocarina tourism managers must also be active in disseminating or promoting tourist attractions.

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